

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of 2-Methylpropan-1-ol by Cerium(IV) in Sulphuric Acid Medium

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Kinetic studies of most of the primary¹ and secondary² alcohols have been carried out using cerium(IV) as an oxidant but so far none has chosen 2-methylpropan-1-ol as the substrate. It may be due to the much slower reaction of this substrate compared to other alcohols. The present communication deals with the kinetic study of the oxidation of 2-methylpropan-1-ol by cerium(IV) in 2.0 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ medium at an ionic strength of 0.5 mol dm⁻³ in the temperature range 40–70°.

Results and Discussion

The pseudo-first order rate constant (*k'*) increases with increase in [alcohol] in the range of 0.1–0.7 mol dm⁻³. The second order rate constants, *k*₂ (= *k'*/[alcohol]) are invariant at various [alcohol] (Table 1). Under the conditions

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING CONCENTRATIONS ON RATE OF REACTION 2-METHYLPROPAN-1-OL-CERIUM(IV) SYSTEM

[H₂SO₄] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³, μ = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 60°

$\times 10^2 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10 [2\text{-Methylpropan-1-ol}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$\times 10^5 k'$ s ⁻¹	$\times 10^4 k_2$ mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹
1.0	0.5	1.44	2.88
1.0	1.0	2.96	2.96
1.0	2.0	5.69	2.85
1.0	3.0	8.37	2.79
1.0	4.0	11.3	2.83
1.0	5.0	14.2	2.84
0.5	3.0	10.7	3.59
1.0	3.0	8.37	2.79
2.0	3.0	6.40	2.13
3.0	3.0	5.16	1.72
4.0	3.0	4.34	1.45
5.0	3.0	3.68	1.23

[Ce^{IV}] ≪ [alcohol] the order in [Ce^{IV}] is unity as revealed by the linear plots of log [Ce^{IV}] vs time. The values of *k'* are obtained from the slopes of the above plots. Although the first order plots are linear for all concentrations of Ce^{IV}, *k'* is not independent of the initial [Ce^{IV}]. *k'* decreases with the increase in [Ce^{IV}] (Table 1). Such an observation has been recorded in the oxidation of methanol and ethanol by Ce^{IV} in nitric acid medium³. The decrease in rate may be due to the formation of unreactive dimeric cerium(IV) species⁴ which increases with an increase in [Ce^{IV}]. To corre-

late the decrease in rate with increase in [Ce^{IV}] in 2.0 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ medium, the following reactions are proposed :

The formation of free radical $\dot{\text{R}}$ in the reaction is established by the induced polymerisation of acrylonitrile in nitrogen atmosphere. In the absence of alcohol there is no reaction between Ce^{IV} and acrylonitrile confirming that Ce^{IV} behaves as an one-electron oxidant and a free radical is generated during the oxidation process.

The rate of disappearance of [Ce^{IV}] as calculated from equations (1–4) is given by

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{2k'k_2[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{ROH}]}{1 + K_1[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] + K_2[\text{ROH}]} \quad (5)$$

The linear plot of 1/*k'* vs [Ce^{IV}] is consistent with the above rate law. Since the plot of *k'* vs [ROH] passes through the origin, it is assumed that {1 + *K*₁ [Ce^{IV}]} > *K*₂[ROH]. The correlation between the rate law and the experimental rate and [Ce^{IV}] justifies the existence of the dimeric Ce^{IV} species in aqueous H₂SO₄ medium.

Effect of acid strength : The strength of H₂SO₄ is varied from 0.5 to 7.0 mol dm⁻³ at 60° keeping all other variables constant. There is progressive increase in the reaction rate with increase in acid concentration, but the rate is retarded when [H⁺] is greater than 3.0 mol dm⁻³ (Table 2). It may be due to the autocatalytic activity of HSO₄⁻ ion which removes the reactive Ce(SO₄)₂ species⁵ by the reactions,

Therefore,

$$[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2] = \frac{[\text{H}_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4]^{2-}}{k_1'k_1''[\text{HSO}_4^-]}$$

As the reactive $[\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2]$ decreases, the rate should decrease with the increase in the $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ and it has been observed when various concentrations of KHSO_4 are used at constant $[\text{H}^+]$ (Table 3). $\text{H}_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^{2-}$ ion is found to be unreactive species⁶.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ IN Ce^{IV} OXIDATION OF 2-METHYLPROPAN-1-OL

$[\text{2-Methylpropan-1-ol}] = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 60°

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	$\times 10^5 k'$ s^{-1}
0.25	1.67
0.5	3.86
1.0	5.40
1.5	6.73
2.0	8.45
2.5	9.90
3.0	11.5
3.5	7.59
4.0	4.70
4.5	4.12
5.0	3.66
5.5	3.08
6.0	2.46
6.5	1.94
7.0	1.38

Effect of ionic strength : The effect of added salt K_2SO_4 has been studied in the concentration range 0.3–1.5 mol dm^{-3} . It is observed that there is no change in the rate constant for the change in ionic strength. A plot of $\log k'$ vs $\sqrt{\mu}$ gives a linear plot with zero slope

Mechanism : On the basis of the results obtained, the following mechanism is suggested :

The mechanism proposes a non-symmetrical transition state. The intermediate complex slowly decomposes to form the radical which takes up another Ce^{IV} at a faster rate to

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARYING $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ ON k'

$[\text{2-Methylpropan-1-ol}] = 0.3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 60°, $\mu = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

$[\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4]$ mol dm^{-3}	$\times 10^5 k'$ s^{-1}	$10^4 k_2$ $\text{mol}^{-1} \text{dm}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$
0.25	9.33	3.11
0.50	8.71	2.90
0.75	8.02	2.67
1.00	7.38	2.46
1.25	6.90	2.30
1.50	6.32	2.11
1.75	5.65	1.88
2.00	5.09	1.70

form the product. The complex formation in H_2SO_4 medium has been studied in detail⁷ and the equilibrium involves the ions like $\text{HCe}(\text{SO}_4)_4^{3-}$, $\text{H}_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^{2-}$, $\text{H}_3\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^-$ and $\text{H}_4\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4$.

The rate law for the reaction is given as

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = k' [\text{complex}] + k_2 [\text{radical}] [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] \quad (12)$$

At steady state,

$$\frac{d[\text{complex}]}{dt} = k_1 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{alcohol}] - k_{-1} [\text{complex}] - k' [\text{complex}] = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$[\text{complex}] = \frac{k_1 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{alcohol}]}{k_{-1} + k'} \quad (14)$$

Similarly,

$$\frac{d[\text{radical}]}{dt} = k' [\text{complex}] - k_2 [\text{radical}] [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 0 \quad (15)$$

$$k' [\text{complex}] = k_2 [\text{radical}] [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] \quad (16)$$

Substituting the value of $k_2 [\text{radical}] [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ in equation (12)

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = 2k' [\text{complex}] \quad (17)$$

Inserting the value of [complex] in equation (17)

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{2k_1 k' [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{alcohol}]}{k_{-1} + k'} \quad (18)$$

$$= K [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] [\text{alcohol}] \quad (19)$$

where $K = 2k_1 k' / (k_{-1} + k')$

Thus the reaction follows first order kinetics each with respect to $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ and [alcohol].

Inserting equation (8) in place of $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ in equation (19),

$$\frac{-d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{K[\text{H}_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4]^{2-}[\text{alcohol}]}{k_1 k_2' [\text{HSO}_4^-]} \quad (20)$$

The decrease in rate for the increase in $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ is due to the increase in the unreactive $[\text{H}_2\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4]^{2-}$. This also explains the decrease in rate for the increase in $[\text{H}^+]$.

The product of the reaction has been identified as 2-methylpropanal by chemical tests and confirmed by tlc. The stoichiometry of the reaction with respect to [alcohol] and $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ was found to be 1 : 2.

The temperature effect has been studied in the range 40–70° in H_2SO_4 medium. The plot of $\log k_2$ versus $1/T$ is linear. The activation energy and the related thermodynamic parameters are presented in Table 4. A high value of E_a (98.4 $\text{kJ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$) suggests that the rate of the reaction is very slow. It is observed that for about 70% of the reaction to complete at 40° for the concentrations of 0.5 mol dm^{-3} alcohol and 0.1 mol dm^{-3} Ce^{IV} , it takes nearly two days. The low negative ΔS^\ddagger suggests that there is no orderly transition state.

TABLE 4—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS IN OXIDATION OF 2-METHYLPROPAN-1-OL BY CERIUM(IV)

$\times 10^4 k_2 (\text{mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1})$				E_a	ΔH^\ddagger	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$	ΔG^\ddagger	$\log pZ$
40°	50°	60°	70°	kJ mol^{-1}	kJ mol^{-1}	$\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	kJ mol^{-1}	
0.277	0.911	2.850	7.440	98.4	95.6	26.7	104	11.9

Experimental

All the chemicals (AnalaR) were used as such. The sub-

strate 2-methylpropan-1-ol was double-distilled. Double-distilled water was used for solution preparation.

The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order condition. The reaction was followed iodometrically by estimating the unreacted cerium(IV) at different time intervals. The kinetic study was carried out using 2.0 mol dm^{-3} H_2SO_4 . The pseudo-first order rate constants were obtained from the plots of $\log [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ against time by least-squares method. The rate constants are with an accuracy of $\pm 5\%$.

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